

FABRICATION PROCESS OF ALUMINA NANOPARTICLES-DISPERSED-THERMOELECTRIC COMPOSITE POWDERS

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1 Introduction

Energy conversion by bismuth telluride (Bi_2Te_3) as thermoelectric (TE) materials has become very attractive issue in power generation and cooling system in electronic devices due to high TE properties at ambient temperature [1]. The energy conversion efficiency of TE devices depends on dimensionless figure of merit, ZT which is defined as $\alpha^2\sigma T\kappa^{-1}$, where α is the Seebeck coefficient, σ is the electrical conductivity, κ is thermal conductivity and T is absolute temperature.

A number of attempts during past decades have been tried to improve ZT by realizing nanometer-scale microstructure such as grain refinement or nanoparticles in the TE alloys [2]. It has been reported that effective reduction of thermal conductivity by increased phonon-scattering and controlled electrical conductivity or Seebeck coefficient by electron filtering could be obtained from nanocomposite structure consisting of TE materials and nanoinclusions [3-5]. In particular, recently, the decrease of the lattice thermal conductivity by using nano-sized second phase dispersed in the matrix has been treated as an effective issue to improve ZT value. That is, phonon-scattering can be occurred effectively while carriers pass through the dispersed nano-materials when the size is below 10nm due to difference between wave lengths of phonons and carriers. So far, however, investigation on Bi_2Te_3 matrix nanocomposites with separately added nanomaterials has rarely done [5-7], unlike in-situ formed Te precipitates[2] or addition of amorphous nanocrystals [8], respectively.

Here, we report alumina nanoparticles-dispersed bismuth telluride matrix ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_3$) composite powders through a chemical route. The

nanocomposites sintered from $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_3$ composite powders show 15 % lower thermal conductivity than pure Bi_2Te_3 bulk fabricated by the same process without Al_2O_3 nanoparticles.

2 Experimental

Al_2O_3 nanoparticles with size of about 10nm were utilized as nanoinclusion materials. They were chemically treated and made into a stable colloidal solution in the solvent. The $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_3$ and Bi_2Te_3 nanopowders was synthesized by using polyol reduction process of Bismuth(III) acetates and Tellurium (IV) chlorides as precursors, respectively. [For the detailed description on polyol process See the Ref. 9] Dioctylether and 1,2 hexadecanediol was used as a solvent and reducing agent, respectively. Oleylamine, Trioctylphosphine (TOP) was added into the mixed solution as surfactant and stabilizer, respectively. The mixed solution was heated to a temperature of 250 °C under an Ar gas atmosphere. The reactant after a polyol reaction was air-cooled on the mantle to room temperature. The synthesized Bi_2Te_3 powders and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_3$ composite powders were consolidated by spark plasma sintering process (Welltech Co., WL-15-400, Korea) at 350 °C for 10min. The phase of the powders were characterized by X-ray diffraction method (model no. X'pert MPD 3040 with Cu $K\alpha$ radiation). The microstructures of the powders were analyzed by field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM). Embedding of Al_2O_3 nanoparticles in Bi_2Te_3 matrix powders was characterized by a high resolution transmission electron microscopy (FE-TEM, 200kV). The Seebeck coefficient and electrical resistivity of the sintered bodies were

characterized using ZEM-3 (Ulvac-Rico). Thermal conductivity was calculated from the thermal diffusivity measured by a Laser Flash method (LFA 457, Netzsch), the specific heat and the density of the sintered body.

3 Results and Discussion

Scheme 1(a) shows the schematically illustrated key process for making alumina-dispersed bismuth telluride matrix composite powders. The alumina nanoparticles are homogeneously dispersed into surfactant-assisted solvent. The Bi and Te atoms reduced by polyol agents can be formed nearby the nanoparticles and Bi_2Te_3 phase heterogeneously can be nucleated at the surface of surfactant-capped alumina rather than at the wall of flask in the solution system. This process can provide $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_3$ composite powders in which Al_2O_3 nanoparticles are homogeneously dispersed as shown in Scheme 1(b).

Scheme 1. Schematic illustration of (a) heterogeneous nucleation of Bi and Te atoms on alumina nanoparticles homogeneously dispersed in solvent, (b) alumina nanoparticles-dispersed Bi_2Te_3 matrix composite powders.

Fig. 1(a) shows FE-SEM surface morphologies of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_3$ composite powders synthesized by polyol reduction process. The powders has a regular disc-shape with the size of about 500 nm in plane and a few tens of nm in thickness. Several powders have transparent characteristics due to very thin thickness. The XRD patterns as shown in Fig. 1(b) exhibit the clear Bi_2Te_3 phase corresponding to the JCPDS card no. 15-0863 while Al_2O_3 is not observed in the peaks due to small volume fraction below 3 %. A variety of indexed crystal planes including (015) as a main peak indicates that the composite powders consist of

polycrystalline Bi_2Te_3 grains. The Bi_2Te_3 powders without Al_2O_3 nanoparticles also displays similar XRD patterns. That means Bi_2Te_3 phase is well synthesized by polyol process regardless of addition of Al_2O_3 .

Fig. 1. (a) FEM-SEM image of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_3$ composite powders synthesized by chemical route (b) XRD patterns.

Fig. 2 (a) and (b) shows the bright and dark-field TEM image of the composite powders. Many bright spots and gray spots in the bismuth telluride powders were observed, respectively, while there are no spots in only Bi_2Te_3 powders. The point-EDS results on the spot as shown in Fig. 2(c) display clear Al ($\text{K}\alpha$) peak that indicates the presence of Al_2O_3 since Al-related materials is only Al_2O_3 nanoparticles in the synthesized powders.

Fig. 3(a) shows a photo of both samples sintered by spark plasma sintering process. The left-sided and right-sided sample is machined- Bi_2Te_3 bulk and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_3$ nanocomposite with size of 8 mm \times 8 mm, respectively. Fig. 3(b) exhibit the FE-

SEM morphology of fracture surface of the nanocomposite. The grain boundaries are aligned into characteristic direction as shown in Fig.3 (b) and averaged grain size is about 1 μm . The directional grains come from the disc shape of initial powders as shown in Fig. 1(a). The relative densities of consolidated bulks are similar in 98% regardless of addition of alumina nanoparticles.

Fig. 2. (a) Bright-field TEM image, (b) dark-field TEM image of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_3$ composite powders, (c) EDS results displaying Al_2O_3 presenting at the region pointed out in (a).

Unexpectedly, electrical resistivity of the nanocomposites is slightly increased from $2.5 \times 10^{-5} \Omega\text{m}$ to $2.5 \times 10^{-5} \Omega\text{m}$ by the addition of Al_2O_3 nanoparticles at the room temperature. That means that carrier did not pass through the alumina nanoparticles. Compared to electrical resistivity, Seebeck coefficients of Bi_2Te_3 materials at room temperature was significantly 1.3 times enhanced into $-130 \mu\text{V/K}$ by Al_2O_3 addition. It could be described that the basis for enhancement of Seebeck coefficient could be described by the potential formed by $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_3$ interface in the nanocomposite providing energy filtering behavior

[4].

In particular, the measured thermal conductivity of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_3$ nanocomposite was 15% reduced compared to that of pure Bi_2Te_3 in the temperature ranging $25^\circ\text{C} - 225^\circ\text{C}$. Reduction of total thermal conductivity in the nanocomposites mainly might originate from newly formed $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_3$ interfaces which cause carrier and phonon dissipation.

Fig. 3. (a) A Photo of Sintered samples of Bi_2Te_3 and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_3$ composites (b) dark-field TEM image of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_3$ composite powders, (c) EDS results displaying Al_2O_3 presenting at the region pointed out in (a).

From the thermoelectric properties, dimensionless figure-of-merit of the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_3$ nanocomposites was calculated and compared with pure Bi_2Te_3 materials as shown in Fig. 5. Even though The ZT value of the nanocomposite is slightly increased by addition of alumina nanoparticles, the absolute value is not high as expected. Up to date, n-type Bi_2Te_3 synthesized by wet-chemical processes [10,11] shows relatively lower ZT values than that by powder metallurgy (PM) method [8]. In this study, we speculate that the reason mainly comes from the increased electrical resistivity caused by alumina nanoparticles partly agglomerated in bismuth telluride matrix materials.

4 Summary

The $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_3$ composite powders whereby alumina nanoparticles are homogeneously embedded in bismuth telluride matrix powders are fabricated by using the polyol process. The thermal conductivity of the nanocomposite prepared from the powders show 15% lower than that of only Bi_2Te_3 materials. Hence, dimensionless ZT value of the nanocomposite is increased by alumina addition due to good combination between thermal conductivity and Seebeck coefficient despite degraded electrical conductivity. These findings clarify that the employing Al_2O_3 into thermoelectric Bi_2Te_3 materials via a chemical route is a promising method to obtain reduction of total thermal conductivity, which can results in enhanced ZT value.

Fig. 4. (a) Electrical resistivity, (b) Seebeck coefficient measured at 25°C, and (c) thermal conductivity of sintered samples as a function of temperature.

Fig. 5. Comparison of dimensionless figure-of-merit (ZT) at 25°C of the sintered Bi_2Te_3 and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_3$ nanocomposite.

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